

Infectivity of RTV vectors^a collected in rice fields in Bicol, Philippines, Feb and Mar 1985.

Location	Variety	RTV infection (%)	Stage of collected vectors	Vectors (no.) transmitting RTBV (B) and RTSV (S)											
				N. virescens				N. nigropictus				R. dorsalis			
				B+S	B	S	None	B+S	B	S	None	B+S	B	S	None
Cagsawa, Albay	IR42	0	Adult	1	2	0	31	0	0	0	60	1	0	0	2
			Nymph	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	17	-	-	-	-
Ligao, Albay	Masuri	5	Adult	0	0	3	26	0	0	2	9	-	-	-	-
			Nymph	1	0	3	14	0	0	0	1	-	-	-	-
Polangui, Albay	IR50/unknown	0	Adult	0	0	1	6	0	6	1	6	1	0	0	1
			Nymph	0	1	1	8	0	0	0	1	-	-	-	-
Pili Camarines Sur	IR29/IR58	0	Adult	0	0	0	1	0	0	7	64	-	-	-	-
			Nymph	-	-	-	-	0	0	0	2	-	-	-	-
San Fernando, Camarines Norte	Unknown	0	Adult	0	0	0	16	0	0	0	19	0	0	0	1
			Nymph	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	5	-	-	-	-
Daet, Camarines Norte	IR42	0	Adult	0	0	0	13	0	0	0	31	-	-	-	-
			Nymph	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	-	-	-	-
Talisay, Camarines Norte	IR42/unknown	0	Adult	1	0	0	24	0	0	0	44	-	-	-	-
			Nymph	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total				3	3	8	156	0	0	10	261	2	0	0	4

^aField-collected vectors were allowed to feed on TN1 seedlings and the inoculated seedlings were tested in ELISA for RTV.

RTV-like symptoms and tested in ELISA. Leaf samples from Ligao municipality reacted positively to RTBV + RTSV and RTSV. Although the presence of RTV was not confirmed, some vectors collected in other municipalities transmitted RTBV + RTSV and RTSV (see table). At Pili, Camarines Sur, *N. virescens* populations

were very low, but *N. nigropictus* population was high. More than 10% of *N. nigropictus* transmitted RTSV.

Of 172 *N. virescens* tested, 3 transmitted RTBV + RTSV, 3 transmitted RTBV alone, and 8 transmitted RTSV. Of 271 *N. nigropictus* tested, 10 transmitted RTSV and none transmitted RTBV. Of six *R.*

dorsalis tested, two transmitted both viruses.

The results indicate that RTSV is spreading as an independent disease in Bicol and that both *N. nigropictus* and *N. virescens* are carriers. RTSV also occurs in rice fields where RTV incidence is very low or nonexistent. *J*

A new rice disease in Manipur, India

N. I. Singh. Botany and Plant Pathology Department, Manipur Agricultural College, Iroisemba. Imphal 795001, Manipur, India

A new rice disease has been identified in Manipur. The disease appears at panicle emergence, when the glume develops a whitish, powdery growth. If the infection occurs early, the grains become chaffy.

The pathogen was isolated from fresh, diseased glumes on potato dextrose

Susceptibility of panicles at different development stages to *Oospora*, Iroisemba, Manipur, India.

Panicle stage	Panicles inoculated (no.)	Panicles infected (no.)
Emerged	20	0
Milk	20	20
Dough	20	4
Mature	2	0

agar. Young panicles were inoculated with a 7-d-old culture of the pathogen. The pathogen was identified as *Oospora oryzaetorum*, which produces coenocytic, branched, hyaline mycelium. Conidia are hyaline. 1-celled, globose, and 2.3 ×

3.5 μ in diameter.

Panicles at different development stages were sprayed with mycelial bits and a spore suspension prepared from a 10-d-old culture. Milk stage was most susceptible to the disease (see table). *J*

Reaction of green leafhopper (GLH)-resistant varieties to rice tungro virus (RTV) complex

E.R. Tiongco, R.C. Cabunagan, and H. Hibino, Plant Pathology Department, IRRRI

We tested ARC11554, ASD7, Gam Pai 30-12-15, Gam Pai 30-12-30, Habiganj DW8, Jhingasail, Palasithari, and Ptb 18 for reaction to RTV-associated viruses. All the varieties except Habiganj DW8 were resistant to GLH. Single test plants were planted in clay pots and enclosed in mylar cages. One month after planting they were inoculated for

24 h with 1, 5, 10, 20, and 30 RTV viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* per plant.

ARC1 1554, Habiganj DW8, and Ptb 18 had low infection with rice tungro bacilliform (RTBV) + rice tungro spherical (RTSV) viruses or RTBV alone, regardless of the number of GLH per plant. That indicated stability of their resistance to RTV complex. RTBV infection of ASD7, Gam Pai 30-12-15, Gam Pai 30-12-30, and Palasithari increased with the number of viruliferous GLH per plant (see figure). Jhingasail had mild yellowing and stunting but high RTBV + RTSV

Reaction of GLH-resistant rices to RTV complex when inoculated with different numbers of viruliferous GLH per plant.

infection. ASD7 had severe yellowing and stunting but high RTBV infection.

Results indicate there are two types of RTV resistance

- high resistance to RTBV + RTSV

and RTBV alone even with high insect pressure, and

- increasing RTBV infection with increased insect pressure.

In the latter case, however, infected

varieties may not be a virus source for the spread of the disease. Furthermore, resistance to RTV complex is not always correlated with resistance to the vector, as shown by Habiganj DW8. *ℵ*

Rice gall dwarf virus (GDV) outbreak in West Guangdong Province, China

Faan Hweichung and Zhang Shuguang, South China Agricultural University; Xie Shuungda, Zhou Lianggao. and Liu Chaozhing, Guangdong Academy of Agricultural Sciences; and Liu Xiaorong, Guangdong Agricultural Bureau, Xinyi County Agricultural Bureau, China

In 1981, an unknown rice disease occurred on 7,3 10 ha in West Guangdong. By 1982, the disease had spread to 33,333 ha. Disease incidence was 30-40% and caused losses of 1.9 to 4.5 t/ha. Symptoms were stunting, dark green leaves, small light green galls on leaf blades and sheaths, and low tillering. Hybrid rices Shan You I, Shan

You 2, Shan You 6, and Shan You 30 were very susceptible, as were some local varieties.

Electron microscopy showed that polyhedral particles 60 nm in diameter were associated with the diseased plants. *Recilia dorsalis* (Motsch), *Nephotettix*

cincticeps (Uhler), and *N. virescens* (Distant) transmitted the disease. Based on the characteristic gall, size of the virus particles, and vectors, the disease was considered to be GDV, which occurs in Thailand and Malaysia. *ℵ*

Breakdown of Xa 4 gene for resistance to bacterial blight (BB) at Pantnagar, India

M. P. Pandey, H. Singh. and S. C. Mani, Plant Breeding Department, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, India

BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* is a major disease of rice in

the tarai belt of Uttar Pradesh, where it causes up to 80% yield losses. Incidence is increasing, and in 1982 and 1983 some previously resistant varieties were infected.

To identify reliable donors of resistance against the Pantnagar race of the pathogen, we artificially field-screened 101 entries, including international differentials for BB, promising IRRI varieties, elite strains